

HOW DOES THE BODY RELATE TO THE SOUL?

by

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Historically, the ecumenical Christian tradition affirmed that God created humans in his image and as unities of body and soul. After death, humans exist as souls or spirits in an intermediate state until the resurrection. However, this traditional view is challenged by many modern philosophers and Christian theologians. In addition, the recent advances in neurosciences raised skepticism against the immaterial aspect of humanity.¹ The rise of scientism followed by the denial of objectivity, universal ethics, and religion resulted in the marginalization of the Christian worldview in academic institutions. In order to meet this challenge, Christian philosophers and theologians reformulated anthropology.²

If the man is composed of two distinct aspects or substances (*i.e.*, body and soul), how does he exist as one “whole” person? How does his body relate to his soul? Does man really have two different components *i.e.*, a material body and an immaterial soul? If he has two distinct substances, where to locate his “personality” and how to formulate his anthropology? Is he an embodied soul or an ensouled body?

In order to explain the mystery of human anthropology, there have been numerous explanations given in philosophical, theological, and scientific disciplines. Some of the prominent positions include dualism, non-reductive physicalism, holism, and *holistic dualism*. Although philosophical dualism affirms the two distinct substances in man, it undermines the material aspect of the body and fails to uphold the unity of humanity. The non-reductive physicalism and holism eliminate the immaterial aspect (soul or spirit) of humanity and thereby fail to represent the biblical idea of man. The traditional view of *holistic dualism* accurately

¹ John W. Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate: A Case for Dualistic Holism.” *SBJT* 13, no. 2 (Sum 2009): 32.

² James Porter Moreland and Scott B Rae, *Body & Soul: Human Nature & the Crisis in Ethics* (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 2000), 7.

represents the biblical idea of man as a unified person of material and immaterial aspects. It is also well supported by the biblical data, ecumenical Christian tradition, and the writings of contemporary Christian theologians and philosophers.³

In this paper, I will argue for the *holistic dualism* position. First, I will present the dominant positions on the issue including dualism, non-reductive physicalism, and holism, and evaluate them against the scriptural data. Then, I will discuss my position *i.e., holistic dualism*, and support it with the traditional view of the church, the scriptural data, and the discussion on brain-mind relationship. The scriptural data of creation of humanity, analysis of death, intermediate state, and hope of resurrection serves as evidence for the existence of the immaterial soul. At last, I will address two of the objections against *holistic dualism* including the notions of an imbalanced Christian orthopraxis and philosophical immortal soul.

Philosophical Dualism

Philosophical dualism has its original roots in “Orphic.”⁴ Some of the prominent variants of dualism include Platonic dualism, Aristotelian hylomorphism, and Cartesian mind-body dualism.

Greek Philosophy

Greek philosophy for the most part taught the dualistic nature of humans. Pythagoreans restructured the “Orphic” myths of dualism and influenced next-generation dualists. According to them, the soul could be purified from bodily impurities by three paths—the ascetic, the aesthetic, and the intellectual. The intellectual path is the highest pathway to purify the soul as it helps to rationalize the soul. When the soul associates with pure reason, it

³ Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate,” 32-33.

⁴ Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate.”

gains the capacity to escape from the body and return to a higher heavenly realm where pure mathematical reason dwells. Heraclitus mentioned that our life begins when we die, and our soul is dead in us when we are physically alive.⁵

Platonic Dualism

Plato developed his version of dualism on the foundations of “Orphic” myths and Greek philosophers. He also formulated a reminiscence theory in which he argues that human beings have immortal rational souls and possess innate knowledge before their birth. Plato taught radical dualism. Humans are composed of a soul of the higher, divine, and rational realm, and a body of lower and mortal sphere. He elevated the status of the soul and mentioned that the soul possesses the attributes of divinity, immortality, uniformity, intellectuality, and indissolubility, and unchangeability. He attributed mortality, lack of intellectuality, multiformity, dissolubility, and changeability to the body and undermined its status.⁶

The soul is considered as a pure reason. It needs to be escaped from the evil and corrupted body and world as they are hindrances to the soul. The desires of the body must be suppressed in order to enjoy the benefits of the soul. He mentioned that the soul is infected with the evils of the body. The body is the source of infinite troubles, ailments, lusts, worries, fantasies, and quarrels. He argues that the purified soul returns to the divine and heavenly realm from which it came. After death, the soul will be absorbed into the universal reason. The pathway to this unification is the purification of the soul through intellectual pursuit and

⁵ Derwyn Owen and Randolph Grier, *Body and Soul, a Study on the Christian View of Man* (Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1956), 38-39.

⁶ Owen, *Body and Soul*.

acquisition of knowledge. Therefore, the origin and destiny of the soul is pure reason, and it finds its true existence only in a disembodied state.⁷

Aristotelian Dualism

Aristotle is one of the greatest philosophers of all time and he is also a student of Plato. Aristotle proposed a *hylomorphic* analysis of the body in which —the body is subject and matter, the soul is the form, and the natural living body is a composite of matter and form. The account of the soul consists of the first stage of actualization and a stage of the essence. He presented a form of dualism in which the matter is potentiality, and the form is actualization.⁸ Aristotle attempted to avoid the dualism of two substances and proposed that man is a unified substance of form and matter of the same substance. However, he returns to a metaphysical dualism as he states that pure form is pure reason unmixed with the matter, therefore it is divine and eternal. Therefore, the reason in human beings is a divine element and a spark of universal “pure reason.” When man pursues knowledge, he can escape from the matter and eventually unite with “pure reason.”⁹

Cartesian Dualism

Cartesian dualism divides the properties into mental capacities and physical materials. Hence, there are two basic types of substances with distinct natures—unextending thinking substance (soul) and unthinking and extended substance (body). Descartes argued that man is essentially a thinking being *i.e.*, soul. Although body and soul are distinct from each other, they

⁷ Owen, *Body and Soul*.

⁸ Fred D. Miller, “Aristotle's Philosophy of Soul,” *The Review of Metaphysics* 53, no. 2 (1999): 310-312.

⁹ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 41-43.

are causally related. He also stresses that the body is not essential for the existence of a person. Man can exist without having a body.¹⁰

Non-Reductive Physicalism

Non-reductive Physicalism

Physicalism is primarily a denial of dualism. However, physicalism is distinct from materialism in that it does not necessarily entail disbelief in the existence of God and non-material beings. The non-reductive part of physicalism does not invalidate meaning, responsibility, and freedom of humanity. Although physicalism is a kind of monism, it specifies the substance to be physical in nature. Non-reductive physicalists believe that there is no soul in human beings. The higher capacities of humans —morality, rationality, and spirituality are explainable as brain functions. They also argue that the moral responsibility of human beings is compatible with physicalism.¹¹ Human morality and responsibility depend on sophisticated symbolic language. It requires a sense of self, capacity to pursue aspirations, and the capacity to evaluate actions.¹² Nancy Murphy summarizes the teaching of physicalism as follows:

“... We are our bodies— there is no additional metaphysical element such as a mind, soul, or spirit. But, second, this “physicalist” position need not deny that we are intelligent, moral, and spiritual. We are, at our best, complex physical organisms, imbued with the legacy of thousands of years of culture, and, most importantly, blown by the Breath of God’s spirit; we are *Spirited bodies*.”¹³

¹⁰ Kevin Corcoran, *Soul, Body, and Survival: Essays on the Metaphysics of Human Persons* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2001), 2-3.

¹¹ Nancy C. Murphy, *In Search of the Soul: Four Views of the Mind-Body Problem*, ed. by Joel B Green and Stuart L Palmer (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 2005), 115-118.

¹² Murphy, *In Search of the Soul*, 125-125.

¹³ Nancy C. Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies? Current Issues in Theology* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2006), ix.

The physicalists argue that our distinctiveness as humans is not necessarily dependent on ontological substance “soul,” rather we need to recognize our humble origins as another species of mammals.¹⁴ The complex functioning of our organisms need to be attributed to the complex organization capacity, rather than, attributing it to an immaterial substance “soul.”¹⁵ The only difference between higher and lower animals is the alignment of consciousness in higher animals.¹⁶ However, Nancy admits that it is a hard problem for neuroscientists to explain how consciousness develops from the brain.¹⁷ Although physicalists deny the presence of a rational soul, they differ on reductionism. A reductive view denies that humans are truly rational, moral, and religious because they do not have a soul. However, a non-reductive view insists that the higher capacities of humans like rationality, morality, and religiosity can be explained as brain functions and associated with human social relationships, cultural factors, and our relationship with God.¹⁸

Physicalists express their concern about the imbalanced approach to biology and neurosciences from the Christian theologians. They argue that humans are closely related to animals according to science and scriptural data. They deny that the Bible does not give evidence for the existence of an ontological immaterial substance “soul.” According to their hermeneutics, the Bible primarily talks about humanity’s relationship with God, rather than providing ontological human anthropology.¹⁹ They argue that our identity as humans is found in

¹⁴ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 55.

¹⁵ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 57.

¹⁶ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 59.

¹⁷ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 60.

¹⁸ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 70.

¹⁹ Joel B. Green, *Body, Soul, and Human Life: The Nature of Humanity in the Bible. Studies in Theological Interpretation* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2008), 70-71.

self-conscious relationality and embodied formative histories of ourselves according to scriptures and neurosciences. Our personhood is inseparably bound up in our physicality and tied to the created cosmos and life experiences and relationships. Therefore, no personhood survives the experience of death. Although Christian physicalists believe in the resurrection of the body, they argue that our personhood is preserved in God's own being after death, and we receive a gift of resurrection from God himself.²⁰

Holism

Holists argue that the Bible presents the human person as a totality, a whole, a unitary being.²¹ Anthony Hoekema argues that the Bible does not teach any strong antithesis between body and soul. Since God created everything good, the body is not evil according to scriptures.²² The holists reject both dichotomy and trichotomy as they do not accurately represent the biblical idea of humanity. One of their arguments is that the terms "dichotomy and trichotomy" are objectionable because they suggest that humans can be divided into parts.²³ They argue that the Bible is not interested in explaining the composition of human beings, rather it provides information on how humans are related to God. The Bible is not interested in the psychological or anthropological constitution of man. J. A. T. Robinson argues that any part of the human being can represent as a "whole" of a human being at any time.²⁴

Holists argue that the Hebrew word "*nephesh*" (soul) refers to the whole person and connotes the totality of human nature, not necessarily represents an idea of the immaterial

²⁰ Green, *Body, Soul, and Human Life*, 178-180.

²¹ Anthony A. Hoekema, *Created in God's Image* (Carlisle, UK: Paternoster Press, 1994), 210.

²² Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 206.

²³ Hoekema, 209-210.

²⁴ Hoekema, 204, 210.

component. Similarly, the word “*ruach*” (spirit) refers to an animating spirit which is the seat of emotion and organ of mental acts and it overlaps with the word “*nephesh*.” In any case, it should not be considered as a separable aspect of humans, rather, it refers to the whole person from a certain standpoint. They deduce that the worldview of the Old Testament was always the wholeness of a person and there was no hint of dichotomy or trichotomy.²⁵ Similarly, the Greek words “*psyche*” (equivalent to Hebrew word “*nephesh*”) and “*pneuma*” (equivalent to Hebrew word “*ruach*”) in the New Testament often refer to the whole man to represent the fullness of life in distinction from the physicality of life.²⁶

Interestingly, although holists argue for the wholeness of humanity, some of them recognize the two sides of humanity—physicality, and non-physicality. They see two complementary aspects of man and consider them to be a mysterious unity. They prefer to identify the man as a psychosomatic unity in order to stress the unity and justify the two sides of humanity.²⁷ In spite of their arguments for unity, they agree that man still exists in an intermediate state (a period between death and resurrection) without a physical body. They argue that Bible does not teach anything significant about the anthropological description of life in an intermediate state, rather it whispers about it. This state is incomplete and provisional and anticipates a future resurrection of the body.²⁸

The practical implications of holistic approach include—church expected to have a concern for the whole person, not limit their services to only one aspect either soul or body, it also demands a comprehensive approach to missions and evangelism, it also affects the way

²⁵ Hoekema, 210-213.

²⁶ Hoekema, 213-215.

²⁷ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 217-218.

²⁸ Hoekema, 221-222.

schools prioritize their instruction, and it maintains a balanced approach to family life and encourages the expansion of medical, scientific, and psychology disciplines.²⁹

Evaluation of the Arguments

Philosophical dualism for the most part emphasizes the ontological distinction between body and soul (or spirit/mind). According to Cartesian dualism, the mind is a distinct substance from the body. The physical body is of the lower realm of earth and it is evil and mortal. On the other hand, the soul is the essence of humanity and it is of the higher heavenly realm and immortal. In order to be delivered from the body, the soul must be purified by intellectual pursuit and suppression of the body. After death, the purified souls will be unified to the pure reason of heaven. This understanding of body and soul is alien to the teaching of scriptures. God created a good material universe and he blessed it. God created man in his image in an embodied form without sin (Gen 1:31). The idea of bodily resurrection in the Bible demands the rejection of philosophical dualism (1 Cor 15:35-58). In Genesis 2:7, God created humans as holistic units of a body animated by God's spirit. There is no indication of partitive substances. Hence, philosophical dualism does not represent the biblical portrait of humanity.³⁰

Non-reductive physicalists teach that there is no soul in human beings and the higher capacities of humans like morality, rationality, and spirituality are explainable as brain functions. Although they believe in resurrection, they do not believe in an intermediate state of souls. According to them, our personalities are mysteriously sustained by God till the resurrection. However, Nancy admits that it is a hard problem for neuroscientists to explain how consciousness develops from the brain.³¹ In contrary to the physicalist view, there was no strong

²⁹ Hoekema, 222-225.

³⁰ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 49-54.

³¹ Murphy, *Bodies and Souls, or Spirited Bodies*, 60.

empirical evidence for the correlation between mental events and brain events. The occurrences of the brain are dependent on the mental activities of a person. Although it is not possible to establish a *holistic dualism* on this information, the evidence certainly does not favor the physicalist view of the brain and mind.³² On the other hand, Bible clearly distinguishes the immaterial and material aspects of humanity. In Matthew 10:28, there is a distinction between body (*soma*) and soul (*psyche*), and the physical death of a material body is distinct from the eternal punishment of the soul.³³

The holists argue that the human person is a totality, a whole, a unitary being.³⁴ They argue that there is no antithesis between body and soul. Since God created everything good, the body is not evil.³⁵ Interestingly, the holists distinguish the physicality and non-physicality of humanity and stress a psychosomatic unity.³⁶ They argue that Bible does not teach anything significant about the anthropological description of life in the intermediate state, rather it whispers about it.³⁷ In contrary to the holists' arguments, the experience of death indicates that there is a separation of material and immaterial aspects at death (Job 34:14-15, Eccl 12:7).³⁸ The portrayal of the existence of the dead in the intermediate state supports the idea of the immaterial soul. There is a continuity of personal identity between dead and living in the Bible. In Luke 23:42-43, Jesus promised to one of the thieves that he will be in paradise with Jesus on the very same day. Lord's promise implies that they still exist as the same persons in paradise (an

³² John W. Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting: Biblical Anthropology and the Monism-Dualism Debate* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1989), 206-209.

³³ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 117.

³⁴ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 210.

³⁵ Hoekema, 206.

³⁶ Hoekema, 217-218.

³⁷ Hoekema, *Created in God's Image*, 221-222.

³⁸ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 114.

intermediate state) before their resurrection. If there was no intermediate state of souls, it does not make any sense in this promise.³⁹

Holistic Dualism

Holistic dualism refers to a theological position that affirms that—God created humans as unified persons of body and soul, and soul exists in an intermediate state between death and resurrection. The term “*holistic dualism*” captures the idea of the unity of body and soul and allows the possibility of the personal existence of a human being without a physical body. There are two kinds of *holistic dualism* advocated by traditional Christian theologians. *Substance dualism* states that the soul and body are distinct substances that are united to form a whole human being. This view is maintained by Augustine, Anselm, Eastern Orthodox tradition, Calvin, many Protestant theologians, and contemporary Christian philosophers. *Soul-matter dualism* states that humans possess a substantial soul which informs matter to comprise a bodily human form. Therefore, humans being is not a composition of two substances but one being consisting of a spiritual soul and matter. This position is originally proposed by Thomas Aquinas; therefore, it is also called *Thomistic dualism*. Most Roman Catholics, some traditional Protestants, and some contemporary Christian philosophers adhere to this position. All dualists support that body and soul are distinct and the soul can survive apart from the body. In this paper, a *holistic dualism* is being argued as a biblical model without focusing on the specificity and type of *holistic dualism*.⁴⁰

³⁹ Cooper, 127-128.

⁴⁰ Cooper, “The Current Body-Soul Debate,” 32-34.

In this paper, the argument for *holistic dualism* is supported by the following—ecumenical tradition, scriptural data of creation of humanity, death experience, intermediate state, and the hope of resurrection, and the relationship between brain and mind.

Holistic Dualism in Ecumenical Tradition

Early church fathers like Clement of Alexandria, Origen, and Augustine upheld the view of *holistic dualism*. Although they believed in the distinct substance of humanity, they refused to undermine the role of the body. They refused the gnostic dualism and taught the goodness of the physical universe and humanity as they were created by God. They upheld the resurrection of the physical body. They grounded their human anthropology in the biblical doctrine of creation and resurrection of the body.⁴¹ Some of the early church fathers including Clement of Alexandria, Origen, and Gregory of Nyssa were trichotomists. According to them, the spirit is the essential human self, and the soul is the mediator between spirit and body. Later, the dichotomy view triumphed over trichotomy and emerged as the orthodox view of the church.⁴²

Augustine of Hippo affirmed the unity of human nature and taught that humanity is the soul which operates the body. He emphasized that man is the unity of soul and body. The soul is superior to the body because it is a simple substance and immortal. Augustine's anthropology is called a two-substance dualism. According to him, the soul permeates and animates the entire body, and the body depends on the soul for its existence. Medieval scholastic philosopher Thomas Aquinas dependent on Aristotle to explain the unity of human nature and insisted on the intimate correlation of soul and body. However, he also maintained that the soul is distinct from

⁴¹ Owen, *Body and Soul*, 52-54.

⁴² Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 8-9.

the body and it survives physical death. The protestant reformer John Calvin agreed with the Augustinian Platonism. Calvin defended the intermediate state and affirmed the conscious fellowship with Christ.⁴³

Creation of Humanity

First, the creation account gives the necessary clues to understand the two origins and dual aspects of humanity. God created man in his image to reflect his glory and exercise his dominion on the earth (Gen 1:26-27). When God created man, He created him as an embodied person. God fashioned man into a bodily form (*basar*) out of the dust of the earth. He breathed the breath of life (*neshama*) into his nostrils and man became a living being (Gen 2:7). The breath (*neshama*) is also considered as the wind or spirit (*ruah*) which is an immaterial aspect. Hence, the origin of man involves two separate sources—the earthly component of the dust of the earth and the heavenly component of the breath of life.⁴⁴ Now, it is evident that man has a visible material body according to scripture and common sense. However, scripture also teaches that man is also dependent on another life-giving force “the breath of life” for his survival (Job 42:7, 34:14-15). Man is not considered as a living “soul” (*nepes*) until the material body receives the breath of life from God. Peter Gentry opinions that —“the soul” is the joining of material and immaterial aspects and it refers to the wholeness of man as an animated body with the life of God according to the Old Testament.⁴⁵ Although the words “soul” (Heb. *Nephesh* and Gk. *psyche*) and “spirit” (Heb. *ruach* and Gk. *pneuma*) were used interchangeably in the Bible, they help to recognize an immaterial aspect of human beings in a material body. This view of creation

⁴³ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 10-12.

⁴⁴ Peter Gentry, “Sexuality: On Being Human and Promoting Social Justice,” *Christian Psychology* 8, no. 1 (2014): 49-52.

⁴⁵ Gentry, “Sexuality,” 52-54.

is compatible with that traditional idea of death —separation of the immaterial aspect (soul or spirit) of a person from the material body (Ecc 12:7).⁴⁶

Distinction Between Body and Soul

Second, the Bible distinguishes the immaterial and material aspects of humanity. In Matthew 10:28, Jesus signifies the importance of fearing the right authority. He emphasizes that his disciples should not fear the one who kills the body (*soma*) and cannot kill the soul (*psyche*), rather they should fear the one who can kill both body and soul. In this passage, it is clear that there is a distinction between body (*soma*) and soul (*psyche*). This also implies that the death of a material body is different from the eternal punishment of the soul.⁴⁷

The Depiction of Death

Third, the depiction of death in the Bible indicates that there is a separation of material and immaterial aspects at death. In Job 34:14-15, Job's friend reveals that God gathers the spirit to himself and the dust (material body) returns to the earth. In Ecclesiastes 12:7, the author portrays that when a person dies, the dust (material body) returns to the earth and the spirit (*ruach*) (immaterial aspect) returns to God who granted it. This is attested by the evidence from the New Testament. In Mathew 27:50 and John 19:30, at the time of his death, Jesus gave up his spirit to God.⁴⁸

⁴⁶ Wayne A. Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Leicester, England: InterVarsity Press, 1994), 473-475.

⁴⁷ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 117.

⁴⁸ Cooper, 114.

Intermediate Stage

Fourth, the portrayal of the existence of the dead in an intermediate state supports the idea of an immaterial soul. There is a continuity of personal identity between dead and living in the Old Testament. Although Samuel was dead, he was still appeared in a recognizable form (quasi-bodily form or ghostly form) with his own personality. He possessed the ability to communicate consciously after he woke up from his resting state. It indicates that the dead are capable of doing activities.⁴⁹ The ghostly form of Samuel is possibly an immaterial soul (*nephesh* or *ruach*) because his body is already decomposed.⁵⁰

Similarly, in the New Testament, the dead are referred as spirits (*pneuma*) and souls (*psyche*) and they exist in an intermediate state. In Luke 16:19-31, the parable of Lazarus and the rich man suggest an imaginative intermediate state. After the death of Lazarus and the rich man, they still exist in some realm, Lazarus went to be with Abraham in a comfortable place, and the rich man suffered torment in Hades. Although there was no resurrection at this point, there was a great separation between them.⁵¹

In Luke 20:37-38, in response to Sadducees' query, Jesus affirms the resurrection of the dead and asserts that God is not the God of the dead, but of the living. He further clarifies that all are alive to God. If they do not have a non-material existence, it is not possible for God to relate to them. God's covenantal faithfulness is tied to the sustenance of his people. This implies that saints are preserved in an intermediate state.⁵² There is no indication of a cessation of

⁴⁹ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 59.

⁵⁰ Cooper, 68-69.

⁵¹ Cooper, 124-125.

⁵² Cooper, 120.

personhood at death and recreation at the resurrection. Instead, they are considered to be alive to God in that stage of an intermediate state.⁵³

In Luke 23:42-43, Jesus promised to one of the thieves that he will be in paradise with Jesus on the very same day. The thief had a heart of repentance and faith at the very last stage of his life. He had a hope of resurrection and the future kingdom of Christ. However, Jesus promised a near-future experience and blessing of his fellowship on the very same day in paradise. Both the bodies of Lord Jesus and the thief died on the same day. However, Lord's promise implies that they still exist as the same persons in paradise (an intermediate state) before their resurrection. If there was no intermediate state of souls, it does not make any sense in this promise of paradise.⁵⁴

In 1 Thessalonians 4:13-18, Paul reveals the state of deceased saints prior to their resurrection. There was no immediate resurrection of the dead, but there is waiting period between death and resurrection in the second coming. In 2 Corinthians 5:1-10, Paul described the state of a person without body as naked. This is a disembodied state till he receives the glorified body.⁵⁵ In Philippians 1:21-24, Paul expresses his hope in an immediate fellowship with Christ after his death.⁵⁶ In 1 Peter 3:19-20, the author mentioned that spirits are in the prison. In Hebrews 12:23, the author described the relationship of human spirits in heavenly realm. In Revelation 6:9-11, apostle John illustrates the presence of souls of martyrs in the heavenly realm and their prayers at the heavenly altar. These passages indicate that human spirits exist apart from their material bodies.⁵⁷

⁵³ Cooper, 112.

⁵⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 127-128.

⁵⁵ Cooper, 145-148.

⁵⁶ Cooper, 151.

⁵⁷ Cooper, 112-115.

The Hope of Resurrection

Fifth, the hope of resurrection indicates the possibility of the existence of the soul and the continuity of personhood between death and resurrection. Psalmists clearly expressed their hope in God beyond this lifetime. In Psalm 15, the author expressed that God would deliver his soul from Sheol (underground). This expression implies that God is capable of delivering a person from the bondage of death. In Psalm 73:26, the author expressed that he would trust God even if his flesh decays. It indicates his hope beyond death. In Psalm 16:10, the author assures that God will not let his people decay and decompose in the grave. It implies that there is a firm hope in the resurrection in spite of the decomposition of the body. Clearly, the people of the Old Testament believed in a life after death and imagined a life in fellowship with their covenantal God.⁵⁸

Isaiah 26:19 affirms the resurrection of the dead. God raised the dead bones to life in Ezekiel 37. Although it was a prophetic illustration, it suggests that God is capable of resurrecting his people. Daniel 12:12 reveals that the dead people will be resurrected and some of them will inherit eternal life and others eternal judgment. If the dead people in the Old Testament had a hope of resurrection, it implies that there is a continuity of their personhood and therefore, it demands an ontological dualism.⁵⁹ Although Old Testament people viewed human beings as holistic persons and psychosomatic unities, they still believed that human persons still exist after death in some form and believed in the resurrection. This implies that they upheld the holistic dualism.⁶⁰

⁵⁸ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 62-63.

⁵⁹ Cooper, 65-66.

⁶⁰ Cooper, 70.

Similarly, the authors of the New Testament asserted the hope of resurrection and indicated the continuity of personhood afterlife. In John 5:28-29, the apostle John affirmed that all the men will hear the voice of God will rise from the graves—the righteous to eternal life and the wicked people to eternal condemnation. There is a clear survival of personhood even after death and resurrection. Those who have done wicked things will not participate in the eternal life of the justified saints. Their sins will remain with them (John 9:41). Jesus also affirmed the resurrection of saints on the basis of their faith in Christ. Although they die physically, they will be raised by his power (John 11:23-24).⁶¹

The Relationship Between Brain and Mind

At last, modern science sheds new light on human thoughts, sensations, emotions, and their association with chemical and electrical stimulation of the brain. The dependence of the mind on the physical brain seemed to deny the possibility of an immaterial component (soul) in the human body. However, science does not help us to understand the complex relationship between mind and brain in its fullness. There was no strong empirical evidence for the correlation between mental events and brain events. In contrary to the expectation of materialists, the occurrences of the brain are dependent on the mental activities of a person. Although it is not possible to establish dualistic holism on this information, the evidence certainly does not favor the materialist view of the brain and mind.⁶²

⁶¹ Cooper, 120-121.

⁶² Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 206-209.

Objections against Holistic Dualism

Some Christians argue that traditional dualism (holistic) undermines the Christian orthopraxis. Some theologians argue that body-soul distinction promotes intellectualism and suppresses evangelism, missions, and service. Liberation theologians express their concern over social justice and argue that holistic dualism undermines human responsibility. In spite of their claims, there is no correlation between body-soul distinction and false dichotomies of nature-grace and intellectualism-quietism, etc., Theological dualism does not necessarily contribute to the religious, functional, and social dualism. Cooper stated that it is absolutely possible to believe in the intermediate state and value the current life as embodied humans for the glory of God.⁶³

Some theologians argue that the idea of holistic dualism entitles the platonic concept of the immortal soul. They claim that the notion of the existence of the soul after death and its non-earthly nature has its roots in Greek philosophy. However, Christian understanding of soul is distinct from the Platonic and Greek philosophy of soul with inherent immortality. According to Christian dualists, God sustains the soul after physical death by his power and embodies it with a glorified body in the resurrection. The body is not inherently evil according to holistic dualism. The Christian view of holistic dualism and immortality of the soul is distinct from the platonic view of the immortal soul.⁶⁴

Conclusion

Although the ecumenical Christian tradition affirmed the survival of the soul in an intermediate state between death and resurrection, this traditional view of *holistic dualism* has been challenged by many modern philosophers and Christian theologians. The recent advances

⁶³ Cooper, 180-182, 190.

⁶⁴ Cooper, *Body, Soul, and Life Everlasting*, 196-198.

in neurosciences raised skepticism against the immaterial aspect of humanity. In order to explain the mystery of human anthropology, there have been numerous explanations given in philosophical, theological, and scientific disciplines. Some of the prominent positions include dualism, non-reductive physicalism, holism, and holistic dualism. Although philosophical dualism affirms the two distinct substances in man, it undermines the material aspect of the body and fails to uphold the unity of humanity. The non-reductive physicalism and holism eliminate the immaterial aspect (soul or spirit) of humanity and thereby fail to represent the biblical idea of man. The traditional view of *holistic dualism* accurately represents the biblical idea of man as a unified person of material and immaterial aspects. It is also well supported by the biblical data and the ecumenical Christian tradition. First, the scriptural data suggests that the creation account gives the necessary clues to understand the two origins and dual aspects of humanity. Second, the Bible distinguishes the immaterial and material aspects of humanity in their composition. Third, the depiction of death in the Bible indicates that there is a separation of material and immaterial aspects at death. Fourth, the portrayal of the existence of the dead in an intermediate state supports the idea of an immaterial soul. Fifth, the hope of resurrection indicates the possibility of the existence of the soul and the continuity of personhood between death and resurrection. Therefore, it is evident that human anthropology is *holistic dual i.e.*, unified unities of both immaterial soul and material body.⁶⁵

⁶⁵ Cooper, "The Current Body-Soul Debate," 32-33

Moreland and Rae, *Body & Soul*, 7-8.

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